

Backbone and sidechain NMR assignments for the ribosome maturation factor RbfA from *Escherichia coli*

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Abstract

RbfA (ribosome binding factor A; 15.2 kDa) is a protein involved in ribosome biogenesis and has been shown to be important for growth at low temperatures and act as a suppressor for a cold-sensitive mutation (C23U) in the ribosomal RNA of the small 30S ribosomal subunit. The 3D structure of isolated RbfA has been determined from several organisms showing that RbfA has type-II KH-domain fold topology similar to the KH domain of another assembly factor Era whose overexpression can complement the deletion of rbfA, suppressing both the cold sensitivity and the abnormal accumulation 17S rRNA in rbfA knockout stains. Interestingly a variant of RbfA used in previous NMR studies, RbfA Δ 25, truncated at the C-terminal domain to remove 25 unstructured residues that lead to aggregation at room temperature, was biologically active meaning that it could complement a knock-out of wildtype RbfA, but it did not act as a suppressor for a 16S cold-sensitive mutation (C23U) nor did it interact stably with the 30S subunit. To complement this work, we report the ¹H, ¹³C, and ¹⁵N backbone and sidechain NMR resonance assignments of full length RbfA from *Escherichia coli* measured at physiological conditions (pH=7.6). This construct contains seven additional residues related to cloning (one alanine and six residues from the HRV 3C cleavage site) at the C-terminus and no aggregation issues were observed over a week at 293K. The assignment data has been deposited in the BMRB data bank under Accession No. 27857.

Abbreviations

IPTG Isopropyl-thio- β -D-galactoside

E. coli *Escherichia Coli*

RimP Ribosome maturation factor P

PIC Protease inhibitor cocktail

TCEP tris(2-carboxyethyl)-phosphine

RCI random coil index

Keywords

Biological context

During ribosome biogenesis a number of assembly factor proteins modify the folding landscape of the ribosome by promoting structural conformations that guide proper RNA folding and/or protein-RNA interactions. The ribosome assembly factor RbfA from *Escherichia coli* (UniProt: P0A7G2; 15,154 Da; 133 residues) binds to the 30S ribosomal subunit [Dammel & Noller 1995] and is presumed to act during the later stages of ribosome assembly to promote efficient processing of the 3' end of 17S rRNA, 16S rRNA precursor [Xia, Ke, Shinde & Inouye 2003], although it does not have any enzymatic activity. RbfA was first identified as being important for cell growth at low temperatures and shown to be both a suppressor for a cold-sensitive mutation (C23U) in the 5'-helix (h1) of the 16S rRNA [Dammel & Noller 1995] and a cold shock protein whose induction leads to adaptation to low growth temperatures [Jones & Inouye 1996]. Accordingly, it was suggested that RbfA interacts with the 30S subunit near h1, consistent with a cryo-EM reconstruction indicating its binding position on *Thermus thermophilus* 30S subunit [Datta et al. 2007]. RbfA homo- and orthologs have been identified and studied in the chloroplasts of *Arabidopsis thaliana* [Fristedt et al. 2015] and the green algae *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* as well as in human mitochondria [Rozanska et al. 2017]. Both chloroplasts and mitochondria harbour a bacteria-like translation machinery, and their RbfA homologs are involved in processing the rRNA [Fristedt et al. 2015].

A 3D structure of isolated RbfA was determined for several organisms, including *Haemophilus influenzae* (1JOS), *Escherichia coli* (1KKG), *Thermotoga maritima* (2KZF), human mitochondria (2E7G), *Thermus thermophilus* (2DYJ), and *Mycoplasma pneumonia* (1PA4). These structures reveal a type-II KH-domain fold similar to the KH domain of another assembly factor, the GTPase Era [Chuang & Huang 2007]. Interestingly, Era overexpression can enhance the effects of *rbfA* deletion, by suppressing both the cold sensitivity and the abnormal accumulation of 17S rRNA in *rbfA* knockout strains [Inoue et al., 2003]. Previous NMR studies of *E. coli* RbfA employed a variant, RbfA Δ 25, that was truncated at the C-terminal domain to remove 25 unstructured residues promoting aggregation at room temperature [Huang et al. 2003]. RbfA Δ 25 was still biologically active and compensated for knock-out of wildtype RbfA, but neither suppressed the cold-sensitive C23U mutation of 16S nor interacted stably with the 30S subunit [Xia et al. 2003], [Bylund, Wipemo, Lundberg & Wikström 1998] [Huang et al. 2003].

We now report the virtually complete NMR resonance assignment for full length RbfA (133 residues) from *E. coli*, obtained under near-physiological conditions (pH 7.6) at 293 K. Of note, our construct features a C-terminal extension by seven residues (-A-LEVLFQ) from an appended 3C cleavage site, which prevented the previously reported RbfA aggregation [Swapna et al. 2001] for at least one week, similar to the RbfA Δ 25 variant, but arguably without its altered biological activity.

Methods and experiments

Recombinant *E. coli* RbfA was expressed in *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) cells. The gene (UniProt: P0A7G2) was cloned into the expression vector p7XC3GH [Geertsma & Dutzler 2011] upstream of a linking alanine and 3C cleavage site followed by a GFP fusion tag (A-LEVLFQGP + GFP).

The initial cell mass was grown at 37°C in Luria-Bertani (LB) media supplemented with 0.33 µg/ml Kanamycin up to an OD₆₀₀ of ca. 0.6. The cells were then washed twice with M9 salt buffer (Na₂HPO₄, KH₂PO₄, NaCl, pH 7.4) and transferred into pre-warmed M9 media complemented with 0.33 µg/ml Kanamycin, 2 g/l (U-¹³C₆, 98%) D-Glucose, and 1 g/l ¹⁵NH₄Cl (¹⁵N, 99%) as the sole carbon and nitrogen sources, respectively. After a restart in cell grow was notified IPTG was added to a final concentration of 0.5 mM for induction. Subsequent protein expression was done for 16 hours at 18°C shaking the culture at 200rpm. The cells were harvested by centrifugation (30 min, 5000×g, 4°C) and frozen at -80°C.

The cell pellet was subsequently thawed in lysis buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.8, 300 mM NaCl, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 1% Triton X-100, 1 mg/ml Lysozyme, EDTA free PIC from Roche) and lysed by sonication for 5 min. The supernatant was separated by centrifugation at 125000 × g and 4° C for 30 min. The soluble protein fraction was injected onto a 5 ml HisTrap column (GE Healthcare) equilibrated in loading buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.8, 300 mM NaCl, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol). The protein was eluted by an increasing imidazol concentration (up to 250 mM) and, after imidazol removal in a HiPrep™ 26/10 desalting column, the C-terminal GFP-tag was cleaved by overnight incubation with 3C protease (1 mg/mL) at 4°C. Free RbfA was separated by reverse affinity HisTrap Column and preparative size exclusion chromatography in a HiLoad 16/60 Superdex 75 column (GE Healthcare) equilibrated in loading buffer. The eluted fractions were analyzed by 12% SDS-PAGE and the protein purity was further confirmed by mass spectroscopy. The final protein concentration was determined spectrophotometrically at 280 nm, using an extinction coefficient of 4470 M⁻¹cm⁻¹.

NMR spectroscopy

Purified [U-¹³C, ¹⁵N] labeled RbfA was exchanged into NMR buffer (10 mM HEPES pH 7.6, 6mM MgCl₂, 150 mM NH₄Cl, 75 µM TCEP, and 7% D₂O or 100% D₂O) and inserted into a 5mm Shigemi NMR tube. All NMR experiments were recorded at 293K. A suite of complementary 3D HNC(O), HN(CA)CO, HNCA, HN(CO)CA, HNCACB, HN(CO)CACB, HN(CA)HA, and HN(COCA)HA BEST-TROSY experiments for sequential backbone assignment, complemented by the full set of 3D (H)C,CH-, H,CH-, H,NH-, and (H)C,NH-edited NOESY experiments (all with 150 ms mixing time) for structure analysis, were recorded on a 800 MHz BRUKER AVANCE III spectrometer equipped with 5mm TCI cryoprobe (H/N/C) or 600 MHz BRUKER AVANCE III spectrometer equipped with 5mm TXI probe. ¹H chemical shifts were directly referenced to added DSS (2,2-dimethyl-2-silapentane-5-sulphonic acid); ¹³C and ¹⁵N chemical shifts were then referenced indirectly relative to ¹H, according to IUPAC ratios (http://www.bmrb.wisc.edu/ref_info/cshift.shtml).

All NMR data was processed with NMRpipe [Delaglio,Grzesiek,Vuister,Zhu,Pfeifer & Bax 1995] and analysed with NMRFAM-Sparky [Lee,Tonelli & Markley 2015]. The secondary structure of RbfA was predicted with TALOS+ [Shen,Delaglio,Cornilescu & Bax 2009].

Assignments and data deposition

The ¹⁵N TROSY spectrum of *Escherichia coli* RbfA (Figure 1) shows rather uniform backbone amide signal intensities and a large signal dispersion indicative of a well folded protein with abundant *beta*-sheet secondary structure.

For 119 (87.5%) out of 136 non-proline residues in our RbfA construct (140 residues), the backbone amide signal could be assigned. The residues for which the backbone amide signal could not be assigned or observed (presumably due to strong line broadening from conformational or chemical exchange) are the N-terminal residues S1 to R10, M35, T36, V38, R45, F56, L57, E62, and R90. The sidechain signal assignment could, however, be obtained for 133 (95%) of all 140 residues (including four prolines). The observed chemical shifts allowed comparison with the consensus chemical shift index (CSI) which, in combination with backbone amide HN-HN' and HN-HA' NOE patterns, allowed the identification of the secondary structure elements of RbfA (Figure 2). Thus, three β strands (β 1: 36-43, β 2:49-56, β 3:94-99) and two α -helices (α 1:9-27, α 2:62-87) were found in the sequential order α 1- β 1- β 2- α 2- α 3- β 3. Moreover, two short 3_{10} coils are indicated in the α 1- β 1 and β 2- α 2 connecting loops.

All assigned chemical shift values for RbfA have been deposited in the BioMagResBank (<http://www.bmrwisc.edu/>) under accession number 27857.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Figure 1. 2D ^{15}N TROSY spectrum of $[\text{U-}^{13}\text{C},^{15}\text{N}]$ labeled RbfA (133 residues plus a 7-residue C-terminal extension by -ALEVLQ) in 10 mM HEPES pH 7.6, 6 mM MgCl_2 , 150 mM NH_4Cl , 75 μM TCEP, 7% D_2O , acquired at 293K and 800 MHz. The indicated backbone amide signal assignment has been deposited in the BioMagResBank (<http://www.bmrwisc.edu/>) under accession number 27857. Residual -NHD correlations (max. 7%, from Asn and Gln sidechains) are suppressed below the minimal contour level by the NH_1 multiplicity filter implicit in the ST2-PT module of the TROSY experiment.

Figure 2. (Top) $\Delta C\alpha - \Delta C\beta$ secondary chemical shifts observed for *E. coli* apo RbfA, with the indicated secondary structure elements shown above. (Bottom) RCI derived S^2 order parameters.